

Arce-García, S., Said-Hung, E., & Montero-Díaz, J. (2024). Unmasking coordinated hate: Analysing hate speech on Spanish digital news media. *New Media & Society*, 0(0). <https://doi.org/10.1177/14614448241259715>

Unmasking Coordinated Hate: Analyzing Hate Speech on Spanish Digital News Media

Sergio Arce, PhD. Universidad Internacional de la Rioja. sergio.arce@unir.net (Corresponding author)

Associate professor at the School of Engineering and Technology (ESIT) at the Universidad Internacional de la Rioja (UNIR). Member of the research group COYSODI at UNIR. His main research areas are communication about social media and digital media. ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0578-9787>

Elias Said-Hung, PhD. Universidad Internacional de la Rioja. elias.said@unir.net

Full professor at the Education Faculty, member of the research group SIMI and Director of the master's degree in Inclusive and Intercultural Education of the Universidad Internacional de la Rioja (UNIR). His main research areas are ICT applied in Education, Social Media, and Digital Media. ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0594-5906>

Julio Montero-Díaz, PhD. Universidad Internacional de la Rioja. julio.montero@unir.net

Professor at the International University of La Rioja (since October 2014) and surplus as professor of History of Social Communication (since 2007) at the Complutense University of Madrid. His main research areas are movies, history and media, and hate speech in news media. ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4145-7424>

Funding Acknowledgment

This article results from the Hatemedia project (PID2020-114584GB-I00), funded by MCIN/ AEI /10.13039/501100011033.

Unmasking Coordinated Hate: Analyzing Hate Speech on Spanish Digital News Media

This study examines the characteristics and behaviours of accounts that propagate hate speech through their responses to articles posted on five leading digital news media in Spain on platform X (previously Twitter). Using non-experimental quantitative research, we analyzed 1,345 hate-expressing messages from 173,449 user comments on content shared in the five leading digital news media during January 2021. Network analysis, Homophilic Exposure Index (HEI), regression analysis, and the k-means algorithm were used to identify features that characterize accounts that disseminate low-intensity hate expressions in a coordinated manner, undermining the moderation efforts of the digital news media. As a result, digital news media must develop strategies to reduce the presence of this type of expression and confront accounts that operate covertly in a coordinated manner, using Astroturfing to manipulate debates around the content published on X.

Keywords: social media, digital media, hate speech, profile, users, digital news media, X, Twitter, haters, features

Introduction

The growing prominence of social media platforms such as X (previously Twitter), TikTok, and Facebook has given rise to a hybrid communication model that has impacted and limited the influence of traditional media channels. In these social media, communication strategies tend to be impersonal, with users accessing and sharing content and opinions on various topics. However, the emphasis on emotions and personal convictions has resulted in a situation where verifiable information is often relegated to a secondary role, leading to its progressive loss (Chadwick, 2017; Matamoros-Fernández & Farkas, 2021).

The implications of social media and the hybrid communication model that have facilitated their growth have been examined. Several studies have focused on comprehending the specific contexts, behavioural patterns, motivations, and gratifications associated with the diverse methods of accessing and using news provided by the news media in digital settings (Gottfried & Shearer, 2016; Bright, 2016; Swart, Peters & Broersma, 2019). Additionally, progress has been made in understanding the role of these contexts in detecting and identifying strategies for the dissemination of disinformation content, including expressions of hate that facilitate its viralization, to influence public opinion and electoral processes (Howard et al., 2017; Van-der-Linden et al., 2017; Zhao et al., 2020; Zerback & Töpfl, 2021). The effects of the echo chamber and bubble filter on social media users in digital settings have also been assessed, including constant message transmission and repetition, persistent censorship of non-majority positions, and information saturation (Guess, Nyhan & Reifler, 2018; Flaxmanm Goel & Rao, 2016; Arce-García, Said-Hung & Mottareale-Calvanese, 2023).

There has been a significant transformation in our societies' methods of producing, distributing, and consuming information content (Swart, Peters and Broersma, 2019). This has significantly impacted the relationship between news media, social media, and their audiences. These audiences have become increasingly reliant on social media platforms, which require news media to adapt their messages and formats to the various algorithms used by these platforms in order to reach more users (Meese & Hurcombe, 2020; Karlsson, Van Couvering & Lindell, 2022). As a result, news media has opened official accounts on digital platforms, which do not always effectively manage and moderate the comments generated.

It is necessary to reconsider the role of media "gatekeeper" and replace it with "gatewatchers" (evaluators of the reliability and appropriateness of information), taking into account individual criteria, professional and organizational routines, which shape the strategies (discursive-interactive, authoritarian-interactive, laissez-faire moderation and highlighting of comments) applied by moderators (often journalists). The responsibility falls on these moderators to ensure a minimum level of discursive quality among users and reduce the prevalence of what they view as hateful expressions (Wolfgang, McConnell & Blackburn, 2020; Wintterlin et al., 2020; Paasch-Colberg & Strippel, 2021).

Social media have emerged as significant venues for the proliferation of disinformation and expressions of hate (Sánchez et al., 2022; Barud and Olalekan, 2022). These platforms frequently disseminate rumours, stereotypes, and prejudices against specific groups. This situation presents a challenge for news media, as the proliferation of expressions of hate and their impact on how readers perceive and interpret messages contribute to the polarization of public opinion behaviour (Anderson et al., 2014; Wintterlin et al., 2020; Russman & Hess, 2023).

The current discourse on expressions of hate lacks consensus on their definition (Paz, Montero-Díaz and Moreno-Delgado, 2020; Rossini, 2022). The debate is often centred on the varying degrees of hatred between related but distinct concepts, such as uncivil, hateful, abusive, offensive, and violent expressions (Culpeper, 2021; Esau, 2021; Pelicon et al., 2021). In other cases, different variables are considered, such as expressions that aim to incite hatred towards vulnerable individuals or groups based on various factors (ethnicity, gender, religion, origin, and political beliefs, among others) (Sellars, 2016; Ziegele, Koehler and Weber, 2018; Struck, 2019). It is generally acknowledged that these expressions are marked by their public scope and intention to cause harm. The primary point of contention lies in the severity of these concepts' violation of social, educational, and legal norms in different countries and societies (Culpeper, 2021; Struck, 2019; Pelicon et al., 2021).

The academic community has focused on developing indicators and detection models for hate speech (Papcunová et al., 2023; Thorley & Saltman, 2023). Additionally, research has been conducted to understand the general perception of hate speech (Cáceres-Zapatero, Bradle and Paz-Rebollo, 2023) and to categorize it into specific types based on themes, such as racial motives (Molnar, 2021), sexual (Arce-García & Menéndez-Menéndez, 2023), or religious (Obermaier, Schmuck & Saleem, 2021).

The study of hate expressions encompasses a range of academic approaches, from analyzing the features of messages associated with such expressions to exploring the role of media, journalists, and social agents in promoting disinformation and hate speech through social media (Vidgen, 2019, Vidgen & Yasseri, 2020; Williams, 2021; Paz, Mayaoitia & González-Aguilar, 2021; Abuín-Vences et al., 2022). Research has also advanced in understanding the ability of users to recognize strategies for intensifying political and social polarization (González-Aguilar, Segado-Boj & Makhortykh, 2023; Samy-Tayie, Tejedor and Pulido, 2023). However, progress has been limited in understanding how users perceive and receive expressions of hate and characterizing those who spread such expressions (Malecki et al., 2021). Additionally, there is some research on the presence of hate expressions in news media, particularly in situations where anonymity facilitates their disclosure (Đorđević, 2020; Paz, Cáceres-Zapatero & Martín, 2021).

Limited academic attention has been paid to the strategies employed by promoters and detractors of online expressions and their impact on disseminating hate speech and disinformation (Malecki et al., 2021). Recent studies, such as those conducted by Said-Hung,

Moreno-López and Mottareale-Calvanese (2023) and Sprejer et al. (2023), have focused on the role of extreme right political actors in driving public opinion polarization in Spain and the United Kingdom, respectively. These findings highlight the need to deepen our understanding of the structural characteristics of hate messages and develop research avenues that assess the role of influential and non-influential haters in propagating such content across various social media platforms.

It is essential to recognize that the phenomenon of haters is not solely attributed to automated accounts but also involves human-managed accounts that operate in a coordinated manner to influence public opinion in specific directions (Alhazbi, 2020). These human operators, sometimes called the 'Internet water Army' or 'elite sibylline corps,' are employed by political or economic groups and utilize diverse tactics (Zheng et al., 2017). Moreover, corporate media accounts can serve as conduits for disseminating stereotypes, prejudices, and polarization towards vulnerable populations.

Astroturfing is a tactic that has been employed in political communication, public relations, and marketing for several decades and has now been extended to the digital domain (Sorensen, Andrews & Drennan, 2017; Keller et al., 2019; Pérez, 2020; Elmas et al., 2021; Arce-García, Said-Hung & Mottareale-Calvanese, 2023). The promoters of this strategy use alpha and beta accounts to initiate viralization actions and operate in an alternative and nomadic manner by responding to the interactions on the messages they disseminate and retransmitting the content to influential users on social media platforms, such as journalists and media personalities. This approach is aligned with their respective interests.

The research conducted thus far, including Guess, Nyhan, and Reifler (2018), Zhao et al. (2020), and Arce-García, Said-Hung, and Mottareale-Calvanese (2023), has focused on the analysis of tactics such as Astroturfing in the dissemination of disinformation on social media. It is presumed in these studies that hate speech constitutes another form of disinformation and polarizing resource. The results indicate that most individuals promoting hate speech are not influencers characterized by many followers and high activity but micro or nano-influencers with up to 100,000 and 10,000 followers or less, respectively. These individuals would reportedly employ their perceived anonymity and lack of organization to exploit the connections or vulnerabilities they establish on Social media platforms (Granovetter, 1973). In other words, they take advantage of their 'common character', vis-à-vis the rest of the users, to interact with them in a certain sense only when it is necessary to guide certain perceptions.

Methods

This research aims to elucidate the characteristics and behaviours of accounts that disseminate hate speech through their responses to articles posted on five prominent digital news media in Spain on platform X (previously Twitter). The goal is to verify the application of dissemination techniques employed by such accounts and to discern the customary practices adhered to by those who habitually propagate hate on social media.

The stated general objective will be attained through non-experimental quantitative research, which aims to achieve the following specific objectives:

- SO1: Point out the features that characterize these 'common character' accounts that spread hatred in the market scenario.
- SO2: Identify the processes of dissemination of hate expressions.
- SO3: Determine the traits that help to understand better the behaviour of 'common character' accounts that spread expressions of hate.

- SO4: Establish the number of profiles of 'common character' accounts that disseminate expressions of hate.

The work aims to corroborate the following hypothesis:

- The dissemination of hate speech through digital news media in Spain is carried out by coordinated accounts, utilizing strategies that are similar to those employed in the viralization of disinformation, as documented by researchers such as Arce-García, Said-Hung, Mottareale-Calvanese (2023) and Keller et al. (2019), among others.

The research in question pertains to the data collected during January 2021, which comprises 266,536 messages originating from accounts on the X platform (formerly Twitter) and about news disseminated by the five most prominent digital news media in Spain, as identified by Statista (2020a, 2020b, 2020c) and the Digital News Report (2020): La Vanguardia, ABC, El País, El Mundo, and 20 Minutos.

The acquisition of messages was accomplished by utilizing the Twitter API 2.0 and the Airflow platform. The automation process employed to extract the data is depicted in Figure 1. The messages were gathered between February and March of 2021, encompassing all communications referencing or citing content from the chosen digital news media.

Figure 1. Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) of the data collection process studied.

The messages were scrutinized and refined to ensure standardization, coherence, and practicality by eradicating null, duplicate, and vacuous messages and eliminating URLs, emojis, and references to news media, as demonstrated in this research. This procedure enabled the extraction of 215,301 messages, comprising content disseminated by the media and commentary provided by followers or third-party users. Among these, 173,449 messages, representing comments (responses) contributed by followers or third-party users of platform X, were chosen as the focus of the study.

During February-April 2022, all collected messages underwent a thorough review, one by one, following the methodology outlined in Figure 2. The process was adapted to align with the hate labelling manual (De Lucas et al., 2022), which categorizes messages into six levels of intensity based on their content:

- Intensity 0: Expressions without conveying a derogatory meaning or a clear intention to insult or incite hatred nonetheless carry negative connotations (e.g., using nationality or another characteristic as a derogatory reference).
- Intensity 1: Expressions that, without resorting to verbal aggression, present or describe, objectively, a fact that stigmatizes a specific social group (e.g. falsely accusing someone or a group of wrongdoing).
- Intensity 2: Expressions that attribute negative stereotypes to disseminate a negative image of a person or specific social group (e.g. portraying immigrants as criminals).
- Intensity 3: Expressions that use verbal aggression (offensive, derogatory, or humiliating language) to target a group that is despised (e.g. using the term "son of a bitch" to insult someone).
- Intensity 4: Expressions that contain veiled or implied threats, as well as harassment or joy at death, aggression, or physical harm to someone or something (e.g. taking pleasure in someone's death).
- Intensity 5: Expressions that call for specific acts of physical violence against someone, a group, or something associated with them (e.g. suggesting burning down a church or mosque).
- **Figure 2.** Process of manual labelling of analyzed messages.

The labelling of the study universe and population identified 1,345 messages with expressions of hate (0.77% of the total messages that make up the study population) that make up the sample studied in this work. Nine hundred eighty-one accounts on platform X published them.

The sample data was subjected to analysis using machine learning techniques through the application of Python software and the Rattle interface available in R (Williams, 2011):

- The present study merged the networks collected around the five digital news media into a single data set. The Louvain algorithm was used with the Gephi program (Bastian, Heymann & Jacomy, 2009). The study involved determining the modularity and cluster analysis of the network and assigning values to each node or account. These values included the eigenvector (which represents the importance of the node in the network and identifies its influencers), closeness centrality (which measures the closeness of the account to the influencers of its group on a scale of 0 to 1, with 0 being

the furthest and one being the closest), intermediation centrality (which represents the account's ability to connect other accounts and serve as a backbone for the network), degree (which counts the number of connections received and issued), and degree with weight (which assigns importance to the connections between accounts based on their relevance to the entire network) or average distance length for other accounts.

- The degree of homophily, or the inclination to connect only with similar accounts or nodes on a global scale, regarding the total number of users, is a crucial aspect to consider. Furthermore, assortativity represents the inclination to establish connections between nodes that share equal modularity (high levels) or nodes that belong to different modularities or groups (low). The Homophilic Exposure Index (HEI) variable, which calculates the probability that two nodes or individuals share a common characteristic out of the total links in the network, is used to measure the HEI. This index focuses on sharing specific characteristics, whereas assortativity measures the connections between nodes with similar traits. The calculations for both variables were performed using the network library in Python.
- The other variables were treated as independent in this analysis. The analysis was performed using the Rattle library in R (Williams, 2011):
 - Multiple linear regression, from considering the eigenvector as a dependent variable and developing a graphic study of residuals to observe the quality of the regression.
 - Polynomial regression, taking the intensity of hatred as the dependent variable concerning the remaining variables as independent.
- Undertaking an analysis to determine subgroups of users based on their nature and behaviour through the application of t-tests and the clustering of users using a k-means algorithm. This involves grouping messages with similar characteristics and/or behaviour to identify potential patterns. In this case, the number of clusters to be formed was determined by seeking the highest value in the Dunn index, which facilitates the evaluation of the quality of the clustering. Values from $k=2$ to $k=16$ were tested, with the highest value obtained at $k=7$. As the different variables have different scales, a data normalization process was employed, followed by the return of the data to its original scale for presentation and better comprehension. This normalization enhanced the algorithm's performance without altering the results presented in the study. Additionally, the reliability of the cluster assignment was assessed through an examination of the coordinate discrimination graph sample for the two primary components contributing to the pattern establishment by the algorithm.

Results

The present study identified 1,346 hateful messages within the network of message tracking and forwarding (RT) connections. These messages were distributed across various clusters around the five digital news media examined. The information presented in Figure 3 illustrates the distinctive traits of the 981 users who disseminated hate messages within the context examined (SO1), as evidenced by their intermediation and eigenvector values. They present values close to zero in all the news digital media analyzed. Accounts that disseminate hate speech tend to have limited followers and do not actively seek to amplify their messages by engaging with hub or influencer accounts. Instead, they frequently employ nano or micro-influencer accounts, which typically have 10,000 followers or fewer. This observation, which involves using degrees or degrees with minimal weight, suggests that these accounts possess limited reach unless they are considered a collective entity.

Figure 3. Distribution of position values in the network of distributions and comments around the analyzed digital news media.

One characteristic of the profile of accounts on platform X is their resemblance to those employing Astroturfing tactics. The data analysis reveals that these accounts exhibit shallow closeness centrality values, indicating that they are at the periphery of their respective clusters (Figure 3). According to Granovetter's (1973) theory of weak ties, these accounts serve as effective conduits for disseminating novel ideas into public discourse. Specifically, they achieve this by maintaining sporadic connections and residing outside the primary hubs of opinion groups (i.e., hub accounts or influencers).

About SO2, the data suggest that the most prevalent intensity levels in these messages correspond to levels 0 to 3 (De Luca et al., 2022). This refers to expressions that go as far as violent verbal allusions, using terms that insult, offend, despise, or humiliate individuals belonging to a hated group (e.g., "Son of a bitch"). However, these expressions do not reach levels that imply veiled threats or calls for physical violence. Most expressions of hate do not exceed the maximum intensity levels, likely intending to stay within the limits of crimes established by the Penal Code. This diffusion activity may contribute to the broader dissemination of the messages. These expressions of hate reach a more significant number of accounts as they evade the removal actions of the main attention algorithms of the platforms, fact-checkers, and/or academics who focus on constitutive expressions of crime.

The study of the accounts that disseminate hate expressions (SO3) necessitates a close examination of their characteristics, particularly their tendencies towards homophily (a preference for interacting with other accounts within the same group) and assortativity (the preference of a node to connect with nodes that are similar to it) when grouped alongside the digital news media accounts under investigation (as shown in Table 1). The findings reveal disparate and contradictory patterns compared to those expected for typical accounts. The

assortativity values indicate that the nodes prefer to connect with others familiar to them. However, the degree of homophily is minimal; these accounts prefer connecting with other accounts that belong to different groups than their own. Moreover, minimal, close, or equal average separation lengths exist between the nodes surrounding each digital news media account. For instance, La Vanguardia has an average separation length of X count. This suggests that there is swift and close communication between accounts and that Small-World phenomenon patterns may be at play. Thus, it is likely that accounts that disseminate hate speech would significantly impact accounts belonging to other nodes beyond those they are affiliated with.

Table 1. Homophily values of the accounts in their networks.

	Asortativity	Asortativity Homophilic exposure index (HEI)	Global connections in the network	The average length between nodes
20 Minutos	0.67	0.04	0.16	1.15
ABC	0.64	0.02	0.19	1.25
El Mundo	0.59	0.04	0.16	1.2
El País	0.78	0.02	0.24	1.68
La Vanguardia	0.79	0.08	0.19	1

The accounts that promote hate expressions exhibit high assortativity and low homophily, which is atypical behaviour for a standard social group whose primary relationships are with acquaintances. These accounts have a strong bond within their group but lack similarity. They resemble a global network of accounts organized and utilized to support various groups in a decentralized manner rather than a single group. This structure renders them challenging to identify while coordinated hate messages are being spread.

The next step involved performing a linear regression analysis on the variables related to the eigenvector or eigenvectors (as shown in Table 2) of accounts that disseminate hate expressions. The objective was to determine both their behaviour and common characteristics statistically. The results indicated a highly significant statistical correspondence between the position in the network, as indicated by its eigenvector, and the intensity values (p-value <0.0001), weighted degree, betweenness (p-value <0.01), and closeness centrality (p-value <0.05). This suggests that these accounts are located far from the centre of their clusters, have a low profile, and a position far from the centre of their clusters, consistent with the findings of studies that have addressed the use of Astroturfing strategies in social media (Arce-García, Said-Hung, Mottareale-Calvanese, 2023; Keller et al., 2019).

Table 2. Analysis of variance using linear regression concerning the eigenvector

	Df	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	F value	Pr(>F)	
Intermediation	1	0.01079	0.0107940	7.8957	0.005059	**
Close centrality	1	0.00701	0.0070105	5.1281	0.023770	*

degrees

Grade	1	0.00328	0.0032777	2.3976	0.121857	
Grade.with.weight	1	0.01389	0.0138911	10.1612	0.001482	**
Intensity	1	0.02426	0.0242621	17.7474	0.00002767	***
Residuals	935	1.27822	0.0013671			

P-value note: 0 '***', 0.001 '**', 0.01 '*', 0.05 '.'

The analysis of the linear regression model's residual distribution graphs, as presented in Figure 4, lends some credence to the model's validity. In particular, the Normal Q-Q plot reveals that the fit is not entirely linear and that most residuals are randomly dispersed, with only a few located in the lower region. This conclusion has been tested using different data normalizations and significant variables, and consistent results have been obtained.

It is important to note that this finding does not necessarily indicate a failure of the model adjustment but rather the possibility that certain accounts may deliberately avoid conforming to a standard behaviour model to evade detection. This could be seen as an effort to disguise themselves as "normal" and carry out a premeditated plan, particularly at the level of public opinion. Therefore, despite their similarity in being off the radar, these accounts are considered "abnormal" and would not exhibit a normal distribution. This suggests that they would not follow a normal distribution despite their weakness.

Figure 4. Residual plots in the linear regression model.

Undertaking a polynomial regression Anova, it was determined that there is a statistically significant relationship between the dependent variable of intensity and the remaining values (p-value <0.0001). This finding supports the notion that the intensity of hate is linked to the importance of the account within the network.

In order to determine the number of profiles associated with accounts that disseminate hate expressions (SO4), the k-means algorithm was employed to create seven distinct groups. This decision was based on the fact that this number yielded the highest Dunn index, which measures each cluster's quality of separation and definition. The Dunn value for this study was 0.018, which is relatively small. This finding is consistent with the observation that the nodes or accounts within the network exhibit similar characteristics and behaviours. The discriminant representation further supports this conclusion, based on the two main components or variables accounting for 56.37% of the distribution. Figure 5 illustrates how the seven clusters identified by the algorithm largely overlap, indicating the similarity in nature and behaviour of these accounts.

Figure 5. Discriminant coordinates concerning the two most notable components in the assignment to clusters according to k-means.

The data provided in Table 3 illustrates how the Dunn index effectively forms and displays seven distinct clusters, displaying nearly identical results. However, two clusters, particularly cluster 6, comprise most accounts, with an intensity of hate around 3. Cluster 6 has the lowest intensity of hate (2.81) and the most minor exponent activity (grade 9 and weight 12.34), indicating a lack of prominence. Most accounts within this cluster exhibit an activity profile that could be more notable, with minimal intermediation value. Additionally, they have the

second lowest closeness centrality value, indicating that they are not closely connected to the network's influencers. Cluster 1, the second largest group, has a slightly higher intensity of hate (2.98) but already exhibits more significant activity (grade 109.75 and weight 189.51), indicating a greater level of engagement. This suggests that these clusters desire normality, as they are not highly active or influential within the network.

As depicted in Table 3, the other groups display a relatively minor number of accounts yet exhibit a heightened level of hatred that falls short of reaching level 4 intensity, as assessed in this study (group 4 with an intensity level of 3.02). This group demonstrates substantial network structuring or intermediation, albeit at a reduced capacity. The most active account groups are 2 and 3, boasting grades 3020 and 6766, respectively, with a notable weight. Groups 5 and 7 exhibit an exact intensity value of 3 in hate, accompanied by intermediation values of zero or nearly zero. Despite their minuscule eigenvectors, they are closer to the influencers in their respective networks. Thus, the most active accounts are few but frequently engage in constant hate speech.

Table 3. Cluster centres when applying k-means with seven groups.

Group	Intermediation	Eigenvector	Centrality closeness	Degree	Degree with weight	Hate intensity	Cluster size
1	0.00158	0.01125	0.12531	109,75	189.51	2.980	102
2	0.00000	0.06436	0.48715	1183,75	3305.75	3.000	4
3	0.00000	0.00874	0.72543	3020.00	6766.00	3.000	1
4	0.02300	0.01045	0.08306	231.39	475.55	3.020	51
5	0.09091	0.00848	0.37369	414.14	1050.55	3.000	22
6	0.00037	0.01506	0.02563	9.00	12.34	2.807	752
7	0.00000	0.00507	0.45868	680.22	2102.89	3.000	9

Table 3 presents data that supports previous observations. Despite their similarities, all groups exhibit intense hatred around level 3. Furthermore, this data suggests that highly active groups consist of a few accounts more central to their networks. These accounts could be called "kamikaze" accounts, as they are prevalent on the platform, located at the periphery of the clusters, and have minimal intermediation. They do not play a significant role in connecting users within the network. These accounts, which deviate from Granovetter's (1973) weak link theory of introducing new ideas into public opinion, behave differently and approach the centre of the network for specific purposes, thereby explaining the deviations observed in the linear regression study.

Discussions

The data analyzed in this study pertains to the specific objectives concerning the accounts of five Spanish digital news media on the platform, as investigated by Sorensen, Andrews, and Drennan (2017), Keller et al. (2019), Pérez (2020), and Said-Hung, Moreno-López, and Mottareale-Calvanese (2023). These accounts are categorized as micro or nano influencers due to their lack of a large number of followers, and they attempt to maintain a "low profile" by staying away from the centrality of the different groups in which they engage in communicative

actions, as indicated by the eigenvector values shown in Table 2. Additionally, these accounts do not form structured networks through the studied digital news media, as the intermediation between accounts is nearly zero.

The accounts that propagate hate expressions regarding the cases studied are likely to exhibit characteristics similar to those associated with the employment of strategies such as Astroturfing, as identified in studies on the dissemination of misinformation content on social media, including those conducted by Guess, Nyhan, and Reifler (2018), Zhao et al. (2020), and others previously mentioned.

The propagation of expressions of hate emanating from accounts connected to the digital news media under investigation would occur following Granovetter's (1973) stipulation, which refers to the supposed "common character" adopted by the accounts studied, distinguishing them from the broader audience engaged with the news and content disseminated by the media on platforms such as The distribution of expressions of hate would take place with intensities that do not surpass level 3 of the scale employed in this research (De Lucas et al., 2022). The expressions do not amount to veiled or implicit threats or calls for explicit physical violence against an individual or particular social group and, hence, are not deemed to violate legal norms, even if they are considered detrimental to social and educational norms. These expressions of hate aim to shape public opinion by transmitting insults, negative connotations, and factual data to stigmatize or attribute actions to specific individuals or social groups. This intensity level may enable the accounts to evade detection, monitoring, and control systems for such expressions, as suggested by Vidgen (2019), Vidgen and Yasseri (2020), and Williams (2021).

The behaviour of users interacting with content disclosed by Spanish digital news media accounts would be anomalous or different based on the data analyzed. This behaviour deviates from what is typically observed in accounts that disseminate hate expressions. The analysis of assortativity, connection edge length, k-means, and linear regression revealed that these users do not exhibit association patterns that favour the echo chamber and bubble filter effect, as authors like Pariser (2011) stated. Instead, their groups or clusters are related to many others, and their behaviour is similar to other accounts that disseminate hate expressions. Furthermore, there is evidence of possible coordination between these "haters" accounts around the content published by the digital news media through the accounts of X. This restriction on the "gatewatchers" capacity of these media, as described by Russman and Hess (2023), highlights the limitations of individual criteria, professional, and institutional routines and strategies applied for this purpose.

In light of those mentioned above, the hypothesis under consideration should be deemed acceptable within the confines of this study. Specifically, the dissemination of hate expressions emanating from accounts affiliated with digital news media in Spain appears to originate from profiles exhibiting traits and behaviours akin to stratagems such as Astroturfing (Keller et al., 2019; Arce-García, Said-Hung, Mottareale-Calvanese, 2023). This scenario can amplify the dissemination of such expressions among the general public and, consequently, influence public opinion in favour of specific interests. These interests aim to propagate particular themes and subject-specific social groups to targeted attacks..

Conclusions

In the parameters that define this study (the five top digital news media in Spain and the collection period), a situation is depicted that allows for an exploration of the dissemination of hate speech in recent years in light of misinformation. Both concepts, inherently connected to quickness, are typically utilized as communication tools to elicit reactions and increased

interactions surrounding specific topics, groups, or social collectives. One of the attributes of social media is its exploitation (in this instance, the aforementioned digital communication context) (Chadwick, 2017; Matamoros-Fernández & Farkas, 2021).

The actions above would be carried out, at least based on the data provided, by potentially coordinated accounts exhibiting natures and behaviours similar to those observed in content dissemination strategies such as Astroturfing, as proposed by Keller et al. (2019), Pérez (2020), Elmas et al. (2021), and Arce-García, Said-Hung, and Mottareale-Calvanese (2023). This would create an atmosphere wherein the supposed spontaneity or randomness of the haters' accounts would not exceed the social, educational, and legal norms of those who manage them. Undertaking this endeavour would involve circumventing the legal stipulations in countries such as Spain and transcending the moderators in digital news media on social media platforms. (Russman & Hess, 2023).

Social media platforms have emerged as fertile breeding grounds for the proliferation of disinformation and hate content, as evidenced by recent studies by Sánchez et al. (2022) and Barud, and Olalekan (2022). In the case of digital news media in Spain, there appears to be a lack of viable strategies to confront or mitigate the impact of such expressions. This study found that, although alerts may be an effective means of addressing incidents of intense hatred involving humiliation or hate crimes, these measures were rarely utilized by the accounts examined.

Undertaking a reevaluation of the current moderation protocols and the methodologies applied to determine the veracity and pertinence of remarks posted by users on news articles and shared content on social media platforms is a matter of great importance. Equally crucial is the need to critically examine and implement measures that facilitate identifying and effectively countering "low-intensity or moderate hate" that originates within the confines of these digital communication settings. This is especially true in cases where the behaviour and nature of "haters" studied in this research mandate a comparably indefensible context, akin to a scenario in which a hundred randomly selected individuals would spontaneously execute the same dance steps without prior training or coordination.

A possible practical application of this research is the necessity to reconsider the actions currently undertaken by the moderators of digital social spaces in digital news media and other social entities interested in this phenomenon. Primarily, they must comprehend that expressions of hate are being disseminated by agents operating in concert "in the shadows" and utilizing the shortcomings of digital news media for early detection in order to locate the presence of accounts employing tactics such as Astroturfing.

The need for further study of accounts that promote hatred has been emphasized by Malecki et al. (2022). This current endeavour is not intended to provide the final word on the subject but rather to stimulate contemplation and investigate novel approaches to analysis, with the ultimate goal of enhancing our comprehension of this subject, which has gained considerable attention in both academic and social spheres. It is essential to analyze a substantial amount of data and prolong the duration of the study. Furthermore, employing both quantitative and qualitative methods is crucial for complementary insights. This study distinguishes between long-term strategic approaches and short-term tactical measures employed in promoting hateful messages on social media platforms. It is crucial to analyze not only the digital news media but also other forms of media to understand the various types and intensities of hate speech. By leveraging this project's growing volume of data, we hope that subsequent studies will assist news media and journalists in effectively moderating their online platforms.

References

- Abuín-Vences N, Cuesta-Cambra U, Niño-González JI, et al. (2022). Hate Speech Analysis as a Function of Ideology: Emotional and Cognitive effects. *Comunicar* 30(71): 37-48. <https://doi.org/10.3916/c71-2022-03>
- Alhazbi S (2020). Behavior-Based Machine Learning Approaches to Identify State-Sponsored Trolls on Twitter. *IEEE Access* 8: 195132-195141. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3033666>
- Anderson A, Brossard D, Scheufele D, et al. (2014). The 'Nasty Effect': Online Incivility and Risk Perceptions of Emerging Technologies. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication* 19(3): 373–387. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jcc4.12009>
- Arce-García S, Said-Hung E, Mottareale-Calvanese D (2023). Tipos de campaña Astroturfing de contenidos desinformativos y polarizados en tiempos de pandemia en España. *ICONO 14. Revista Científica De Comunicación Y Tecnologías Emergentes* 21(1). <https://doi.org/10.7195/ri14.v21i1.1890>
- Barud, W., Olalekan, A. (2022). Detection of fake news and Hate speech for Ethiopian Languages: A Systematic Review of the Approaches. *Journal of Big Data*, 9(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40537-022-00619-x>
- Bastian M, Heymann S, Jacomy M (2009, May 17-20). *Gephi: an open source software for exploring and manipulating networks* [Conference]. International AAAI Conference on Weblogs and Social Media, California, United States. <http://www.aaai.org/ocs/index.php/ICWSM/09/paper/view/154>
- Bright J (2016). The Social News Gap: How News Reading and News Sharing Diverge. *Journal of Communication* 66(3): 343–365. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jcom.12232>
- Cáceres-Zapatero MD, Brändle G, Paz-Rebollo M.A. (2023). Stances on hate speech: Population opinions and attitudes. *Profesional De La información* 32(4). <https://doi.org/10.3145/epi.2023.jul.10>
- Culpeper J (2021). Impoliteness and Hate Speech: compare and contrast. *Journal of Pragmatics* 179: 4-11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pragma.2021.04.019>
- Chadwick A (2017). *The hybrid media system*. Oxford University Press.
- De Lucas A, Römer M., Izquierdo D, et al. (2022). *Manual para el Etiquetado de mensajes de odio*. Figshare. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.18316313>
- Digital News Report (2020). *Se debilita la confianza en los medios, resisten las marcas periodísticas y emerge el periodismo local* [Trust in the media weakens, journalistic brands resist and local journalism emerges]. Digital News Report. <https://www.digitalnewsreport.es/2020/se-debilita-la-confianza-en-los-medios-resisten-las-marcas-periodisticas-y-emerge-el-periodismo-local/>
- Đorđević J (2020). The sociocognitive dimension of hate speech in readers' comments on Serbian news websites. *Discourse, Context and Media* 33: 100366. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dcm.2019.100366>
- Esau, K. (2021). Hate speech (Hate Speech/Incivility). *DOCA*. <https://doi.org/10.34778/5a>
- Flaxman S, Goel S, Rao J (2016). Filter Bubbles, Echo Chambers, and Online News Consumption. *Public Opinion Quarterly* 80: 298–320. <https://doi.org/10.1093/poq/nfw006>

- Gottfried J, Shearer E (2016). *News Use Across Social Media Platforms 2016*. Journalism. <http://www.journalism.org/2016/05/26/news-use-across-social-media-platforms-2016/>.
- Granovetter M (1973). The strength of weak ties. *American Journal of Sociology* 78: 1360-1380.
- Guess A, Nyhan B, Reifler J (2018). Selective Exposure to Misinformation: Evidence from the consumption of fake news during the 2016 U.S.Presidential campaign. *European Research Council*. <https://cutt.ly/FOgUe1R>
- González-Aguilar, J., Segado-Boj, F., & Makhortykh, M. (2023). Populist right parties on TikTok: spectacularization, personalization, and hate speech. *Media and Communication*, 11(2). <https://doi.org/10.17645/mac.v11i2.6358>
- Howard P, Bolsover G, Kollanyi B, et al. (2017, March 1-26). *Junk News and Bots during the U.S. Election: What Were Michigan Voters Sharing Over Twitter?* [Conference]. Computational Propaganda Project-Oxford Internet Institute, Oxford, United Kingdom. <https://cutt.ly/kRihRoY>
- Karlsson M, Couvering E, Lindell J (2022). Publishing, sharing, and spreading online news: A case study of gatekeeping logics in the platform era. *Nordicom Review* 43: 190-213. <https://doi.org/10.2478/nor-2022-0012>
- Keller F, Schoch D, Stier S, et al. (2019). Political Astroturfing on Twitter: How to Coordinate a Disinformation Campaign. *Political Communication* 37: 256-280. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10584609.2019.1661888>
- Małeckı W, Kowal M, Dobrowolska M, et al. (2021). Defining online hating and online haters. *Frontiers in Psychology* 12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.744614>
- Matamoros-Fernández A, Farkas J (2021). Racism, Hate Speech, and Social Media: A Systematic Review and critique. *Television & New Media*, 22(2): 205-224. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1527476420982230>
- Meese J, Hurcombe E (2020). Facebook, News media and platform dependency: The institutional impacts of news distribution on social platforms. *New Media & Society* 23(8): 2367-2384. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444820926472>
- Molnar L (2021). The Law of the Jungle. The online hate-speech against the Roma in Romania. *Victims & offenders*, 16(8): 1108-1129. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15564886.2021.1895391>
- Obermaier M, Schmuck D, Saleem M (2021). I'll be there for you? Effects of islamophobic online hate speech and counter speech on Muslim in-group bystanders' intention to intervene. *New Media & Society* 25(9): 2339-2358. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14614448211017527>
- Paasch-Colberg, S., & Strippel, C. (2021). "The Boundaries are Blurry...": How Comment Moderators in Germany See and Respond to Hate Comments. *Journalism Studies* 23: 224-244. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1461670X.2021.2017793>.
- Papcunová J, Martončík M, Fedáková D, et al. (2021). Hate Speech Operationalization: A Preliminary examination of hate speech indicators and their structure. *Complex & Intelligent Systems* 9(3): 2827-2842. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40747-021-00561-0>

- Pariser E (2011). *The filter bubble*. Penguin Books Ltd.
- Paz MA, Mayagoitia-Soria A, González-Aguilar J-M (2021). From polarization to hate: Portrait of the Spanish political meme. *Social Media + Society* 7(4). <https://doi.org/10.1177/20563051211062920>
- Paz MA, Montero-Díaz J, Moreno-Delgado A (2020). Hate speech: A systematized review. *SAGE Open*, 10(4). <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244020973022>
- Paz MA, Cáceres-Zapatero MD, Martín I (2021). Suscripción a la prensa digital como contención a los discursos de odio [Subscription to the digital press as a containment of hate speech]. *Profesional De La Informacion* 30(6). <https://doi.org/10.3145/epi.2021.nov.13>
- Pelicon A, Shekhar R, Škrlj B, et al. (2021). Investigating cross-lingual training for offensive language detection. *PeerJ*, 7: e559. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj-cs.559>
- Pérez J (2020, May 21). "Yo fui un bot": las confesiones de un agente dedicado al engaño en Twitter ["I was a bot": the confessions of an agent dedicated to deception On twitter]. *El País*. <https://cutt.ly/wRihXGu>
- Rossini P (2022). Beyond Incivility: Understanding Patterns of Uncivil and Intolerant Discourse in Online Political Talk. *Communication Research*, 49(3): 399–425. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0093650220921314>
- Russmann U, Hess A (2023). The management of uncivil and hateful user comments in Austrian news media. *Journalism Practice* 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17512786.2023.2189152>
- Said-Hung E, Moreno-López R, Mottareale-Calvanese D (2023). Promotion of Hate Speech by Spanish political actors on Twitter. *Policy & Internet* 15(4): 665-686. <https://doi.org/10.1002/poi3.353>
- Sánchez J, Campo-Archbold A, Roza A, et al. (2022). On the Power of Social media s to Analyze Threatening Trends. *IEEE Internet Computing* 26: 19-26. <https://doi.org/10.1109/mic.2022.3154712>
- Sellars, A. (2016). *Defining Hate Speech*. Berkman Klein Center Research Publication No. 2016-20. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2882244
- Sorensen A, Andrews L, Drennan J (2017). Using social media posts as resources for engaging in value co-creation: The case for social media-based cause brand communities. *Journal of Service Theory and Practice* 27(4): 898-922. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JSTP-04-2016-0080>
- Sprejer L, Margetts H, Oliveira K, et al. (2023). An actor-based approach to understanding radical right viral tweets in the UK. *Journal of Policing, Intelligence and Counter Terrorism* 18(2): 139-157. <https://doi.org/10.1080/18335330.2022.2086440>
- Statista (2020a). *Ranking de los 10 medios de comunicación con más seguidores en Twitter en España en abril de 2020* [Ranking of the 10 media outlets with the most followers on Twitter in Spain in April 2020]. Statista. <https://es.statista.com/estadisticas/518802/Twitter-perfiles-de-medios-de-comunicacion-con-mas-seguidos-en-espana/>

- Statista (2020b). *Páginas oficiales de medios de comunicación más populares en Facebook en España en abril de 2020, por número de seguidores*. Statista. <https://es.statista.com/estadisticas/518580/paginas-de-medios-de-comunicacion-de-facebook-con-mas-seguidores-en-espana/#statisticContainer>
- Statista (2020c). *Ranking de las principales marcas de medios de comunicación online según el porcentaje de población que las usaba de forma semanal en España en 2020 [Ranking of the main online media brands according to the percentage of the population that used them weekly in Spain in 2020]*. Statista. <https://es.statista.com/estadisticas/670743/principales-medios-online-porcentaje-de-usuarios-semanales-espana/r>
- Struck J (2019). Digitale vorwärts-panik. *Monatsschrift Fur Kriminologie Und Strafrechtsreform* 102(1): 54-64. <https://doi.org/10.1515/mks-2019-0002>
- Swart J, Peters C, Broersma M (2019). Sharing and Discussing News in Private Social Media Groups. *Digital Journalism* 7: 187-205. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21670811.2018.1465351>
- Tayie S. S., Tejedor S, Pulido C (2023). News literacy and online news between Egyptian and Spanish youth: fake news, hate speech and trust in the media. *Comunicar* 31(74): 73-87. <https://doi.org/10.3916/c74-2023-06>
- Thorley, T. G., & Saltman, E. (2023). GIFCT Tech Trials: Combining behavioural signals to surface terrorist and violent extremist content online. *Studies in Conflict & Terrorism* 1-26. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1057610x.2023.2222901>
- Vidgen B (2019). *Tweeting Islamophobia*. Doctoral thesis, University of Oxford. Oxford University Research Archive. <https://ora.ox.ac.uk/objects/uuid:3c32d29d-e2e4-4913-abf8-2a28886f55a7>
- Vidgen B, Yasseri T (2020). Detecting weak and strong Islamophobic hate speech on social media. *Journal of Information Technology & Politics* 17(1): 66-78. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19331681.2019.1702607>
- Van-der-Linden S, Maibach E, Cook J, et al. (2017). Inoculating Against Misinformation. *Science* 358(6367): 1141–1142. <https://doi.org/10.17863/CAM.26207>
- Williams G (2011). *Data Mining with Rattle and R: The Art of Excavating Data for Knowledge Discovery*. Springer.
- Williams M (2021). *The science of hate*. Faber & Faber.
- Winterlin F, Schatto-Eckrodt T, Frischlich L, et al. (2020). How to cope with dark participation: moderation practices in German newsrooms. *Digital Journalism* 8(7): 904-924. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21670811.2020.1797519>
- Wolfgang J, McConnel, S, Blackburn H (2020). Commenters as a Threat to Journalism? How Comment Moderators Perceive the Role of the Audience. *Digital Journalism* 8: 925-944. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21670811.2020.1802319>.
- Zerback T, Töpfl F (2021). Forged examples as disinformation: the biasing effects of political astroturfing comments on public opinion perceptions and how to prevent them. *Political Psychology* 43(3): 399-418. <https://doi.org/10.1111/pops.12767>

- Zhao Z, Zhao J, Sano Y, et al. (2020). Fake news propagates differently from real news even at early stages of spreading. *EPJ Data Science* 9(7). <https://doi.org/10.1140/epjds/s13688-020-00224-z>
- Zheng H, Xue M, Hao L, et al. (2017). Smoke Screener or Straight Shooter: Detecting Elite Sybil Attack. *Social and Information Networks*. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1709.06916>
- Ziegele M, Koehler C, Weber M (2018). Socially Destructive? Effects of Negative and Hateful User Comments on Readers' Donation Behavior toward Refugees and Homeless Persons. *Journal of Broadcasting & Electronic Media* 62(4): 636–653. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08838151.2018.1532430>

Submitted version